

BUILDING AN AERODYNAMIC MODEL OF A VERTICAL LANDING REUSABLE LAUNCHER BASED ON CFD AND WIND TUNNEL EXPERIMENTS IN SALTO AND CFD4SALTO

FAR 2025

19.05.2025

Ansgar Marwege, Josef Klevanski, Junnai Zhai, Ali Gülhan

*Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology
Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies
German Aerospace Center (DLR e.V.)*

Jan Vos

CFS Engineering

Funded by
the European Union

SALTO

SALTO

- SALTO - reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations
- funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme
- supports the ESA Themis programme
- T1H hop tests
- Technology maturation for T3 and future launcher configurations

26

Project
partners

12

Countries
represented

38

Months to reach
the objective

2

Flight test
demonstrations

SALTO

CFD4SALTO

- Partners: DLR, CFS Engineering
- Carried out under a programme of and funded by the European Space Agency (ESA) – through the Future Launchers Preparatory Programme (FLPP)
- High fidelity CFD computations and AEDB generation for SALTO
- Support the design of the wind tunnel models used in the SALTO project
- Extrapolate wind tunnel results to flight conditions

SALTO

T1H

Hop Test demonstrator with one Prometheus® Demonstrator to be flown in the frame of SALTO.

High TRL

T3

Reference configuration for future demonstrator version with three Prometheus® engines with more complex trajectory including all flight phases of vertical descent and landing with retro-propulsion

Medium TRL

Future Launcher Configurations

Reference configurations for future launchers with vertical take-off vertical landing. 5 Prometheus® and 9 Prometheus® engines.

Low TRL

T3 mission profile

T1H

Hop Test demonstrator with one Prometheus®
Demonstrator to be flown in the frame of SALTO.

MECO

Flip over

REENTRY BURN

AERODYNAMIC PHASE

LANDING BURN

T3

Reference configuration for future demonstrator version with three Prometheus® engines with more complex trajectory including all flight phases of vertical descent and landing with retro-propulsion

2nd stage to orbit

MECO

Flip over

REENTRY BURN

AERODYNAMIC PHASE

LANDING BURN

Future Launcher Configurations

Reference configurations for future launchers with vertical take-off vertical landing.
5 Prometheus® and 9 Prometheus® engines.

T3 vehicle

- 3 Prometheus engines (approx. 120 t thrust)
- Approx. 80 km altitude
- Diameter 3.5 m
- Length approx. 29 m

Overview

- Modelling strategy
- Configurations
- Coordinate system
- AEDB construction
- Comparison of low and high-fidelity CFD

Aerodynamic modelling strategy

Configurations

- 1st letter: **grid fins** (U = unfolded, F = folded, N = None)
- 2nd letter: **landing legs** (U = unfolded, F = folded, N = None)
- 3rd letter: **engines** (N = no thrust, number of engines running)

FFN	FF1	FF3	UFN	UF1	UF2

Coordinate system

- AEDB needs to cover whole global polar
- Stead of α and β
- Total or effective angle of attack α_s and aerodynamic roll angle ϕ
- Velocity vector of vehicle and free stream and opposite to each other:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{x,a} &= u \\ v_{y,a} &= -v \\ v_{z,a} &= w \end{aligned}$$

range of variation for UFN:
 $-180^\circ \leq \phi \leq +180^\circ$,
 $160^\circ \leq \alpha_s \leq 180^\circ$;

AEDB construction

- Deflect only fin 1 for $\delta_1 = [-20^\circ, 0^\circ, 20^\circ]$.
- Superimpose on other fin positions
- Deltas:

$$\Delta C_i(Ma, \phi, \alpha_S, \delta_1) = C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_S, \delta_1) - C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_S, \delta_{1,2,3,4} = 0)$$
- Overall forces and moments:

$$C = C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_S, \delta_{1,2,3,4} = 0) + \sum_{i=1}^4 \Delta C_i(Ma, \phi, \alpha_S, \delta_i)$$
- C represents $C_{F_x}, C_{F_y}, C_{F_z}, C_{M_x}, C_{M_y}, C_{M_z}$

Assumptions:

- impact of the deflections of the fins can be considered to be independent
- all fins show the same behaviour

Funded by
the European Union

CFS Engineering
Computational Fluids & Structures Engineering

Superposition strategy of grid fins

Strategy 1: rotate the vehicle

$norm(\cdot)$: normalization such that $0^\circ < \phi < 180^\circ$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F2) &= norm(\phi(F1) - 90^\circ) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F2) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F2) &= -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F2) &= \Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F2) &= \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F2) &= -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F2) &= \Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F3) &= norm(\phi(F1) + 180^\circ) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F3) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F3) &= \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F4) &= norm(\phi(F1) + 90^\circ) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F4) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F4) &= \Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F4) &= -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F4) &= \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F4) &= \Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F4) &= -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \end{aligned}$$

Superposition strategy of grid fins

Strategy 2: impose symmetry

$norm(.)$: normalization such that $0^\circ < \phi < 180^\circ$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F4) &= -\phi(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F4) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F4) &= -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F4) &= \Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F4) &= -\Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F4) &= \Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F4) &= -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \\ \delta_4 &= -\delta_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F3) &= norm(\phi(F1) - 180^\circ) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F3) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F3) &= \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F3) &= -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(F2) &= -norm(\phi(F1) - 180^\circ) \\ \Delta C_{F_x}(F2) &= \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_y}(F2) &= \Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{F_z}(F2) &= -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_x}(F2) &= -\Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_y}(F2) &= -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\ \Delta C_{M_z}(F2) &= \Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \\ \delta_2 &= -\delta_1 \end{aligned}$$

Superposition of wind tunnel data (UFN)

Rotation strategy

mirroring strategy

Superposition of wind tunnel data (UFN)

Rotation strategy

mirroring strategy

Superposition of wind tunnel data (UFN)

Rotation strategy

mirroring strategy

Comparison of low-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD (UF2)

- DLR (low-fidelity) $[0,0,0,0]$
- CFSE (high-fidelity) $[20,20,20,20]$
- CFSE (high-fidelity) $[-20,-20,-20,-20]$

Comparison of low-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD

Complete change in behavior

Summary and outlook

Summary

- Definitions of flight configurations, reference frames and free stream angles
- Superposition of grid fin deflections
 - Rotation strategy
 - Mirroring strategy – imposes quarter symmetry
 - Validation with wind tunnel data shows good agreement for both strategies
- Comparison of low-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD
 - Good agreement in complete Mach regime
 - Deviation in higher altitudes
 - Identification of changes in flow field

Outlook

- Second loop of AEDB with Aeroshape 2.0
- Further evaluation of test data of forces and moments
- Cold gas experiments in TMK
- Hot gas experiments in HPTF (and VMK)

Thank you!

SALTO

Funded by
the European Union